

Appendix. Supplementary material

Heavy metal biosorption by Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS)
recovered from anammox granular sludge

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19 **Figure S1** - Determination of the EPS concentration in aqueous systems via UV-vis
 20 spectroscopy. The method can be described as follows. An aliquot of the EPS extract, after
 21 dialysis (3.5 kDa molecular weight cut-off) against ultrapure water, was freeze-dried and
 22 weighted in order to measure its EPS concentration. The remaining EPS extract was then used
 23 to prepare EPS dispersions with lower concentrations via subsequent dilutions with ultrapure
 24 water. The UV-vis spectra in 350-600 nm wavelength range were collected for all the obtained
 25 EPS samples (a). The intensity of the characteristic absorbance peak of anammox EPS at about
 26 408 nm wavelength increased linearly with the EPS concentration: the absorbance/concentration
 27 calibration curve (b) was thus obtained plotting the EPS concentration-absorbance data and
 28 fitting them via linear regression (experimental data reported as average values \pm standard
 29 deviation, n. 3 replications).

30 For the determination of the EPS extraction yields ($\text{mgTS}_{\text{EPS}}/\text{gVS}_{\text{granules}}$; TS: total solids, VS:
 31 volatile solids) all the EPS extracts were analysed via UV-Vis spectroscopy, evaluating the
 32 absorbance peak at 408 nm wavelength, and their concentration was determined using the
 33 absorbance/concentration calibration curve. Known concentration and volume of the EPS
 34 extracts, the EPS extraction yield was therefore calculated as ratio between the amounts of
 35 extracted EPS (TS_{EPS} , mg) and pristine granules ($\text{VS}_{\text{granules}}$, g).

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37 **Figure S2** - Biosorption kinetics of Pb^{2+} (a), Cu^{2+} (b), Ni^{2+} (c) and Zn^{2+} (d) on the recovered
 38 anammox EPS (i.e., percentage heavy metal content remained in solution, and thus not
 39 adsorbed, over time). The tests were performed by treating synthetic heavy metal aqueous
 40 solutions ($C_0=40$ mg/L) with the recovered anammox EPS ($2.82\pm 0.05\%$ w/v as EPS dry weight)
 41 at $pH\ 6.38\pm 0.12$ (see *Materials and Methods* chapter in the manuscript): the EPS sorption
 42 performance were evaluated over time (0-24 h) after centrifugation (10000xg, 15 min, room
 43 temperature). The experimental data were correlated by a first order kinetic model ($C_{M^{2+}}(t) =$
 44 $A \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + A_0$, where $C_{M^{2+}}(t)$ (%) is the heavy metal content remained in solution (i.e., not
 45 adsorbed) at time t ; τ (%) is the relaxation time, correlated to the process velocity and time
 46 required to reach the curve plateau (i.e., sorption equilibrium); A and A_0 (%) are the pre-
 47 exponential term and the asymptotic value of heavy metal content remained in solution, i.e., not
 48 adsorbed, at equilibrium, respectively. Although Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} biosorption by EPS was faster
 49 than Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} uptake, the sorption processes of all the selected heavy metal ions achieved
 50 the equilibrium within 6 hours.

51 **Table S1** – Content of selected elements (mg/kgTS; TS: total solids) of pre-treated anammox
52 granules (0.45% w/v NaCl, pH 5), untreated anammox granules and extracted EPS determined
53 by Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-AES).
54 The anammox-based reactor was again inoculated in the period between two granule sampling
55 campaigns. Consequently, anammox granular sludge used in equilibrium sorption tests could
56 have different properties (e.g., in terms of metal content) compared to pristine granules used as
57 raw material for the EPS extraction: this might explain the absence of Mg in the
58 treated/untreated granules applied as metal sorbent media compared to biomass for EPS
59 extraction.

	Al (mg/kg)	Co (mg/kg)	Cr (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	Mn (mg/kg)	Mo (mg/kg)	Ni (mg/kg)	Mg (mg/kg)
<i>Pre-treated granules</i>	63	< 2.4	6.2	1730	16.3	23.1	12.3	-
<i>Untreated granules</i>	44	10.1	4.4	1950	66	27.1	6.9	-
<i>Extracted EPS</i>	5	-	-	2530	40	-	10	870
	Pb (mg/kg)	Cu (mg/kg)	V (mg/kg)	Zn (mg/kg)	Ca (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)	Na (mg/kg)	Sr (mg/kg)
<i>Pre-treated granules</i>	4.9	33.8	4.1	88	< 2400	< 2400	29000	< 240
<i>Untreated granules</i>	3.35	32.3	3.6	127	7500	17400	29000	< 240
<i>Extracted EPS</i>	-	80	-	320	7050	220	11600	70

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62 **Figure S3** – pH buffer capacity of anammox granules, producing a progressive alkalizing effect
 63 of the aqueous medium due to variable mineral and/or organic fractions present in the biomass
 64 (2.4 gTS/L, **a**, and 0.6 gTS/L, **b**, granule concentration).

65 pH in the liquid bulk (constituted by 0.45 % w/v NaCl solution in demineralized water)
 66 increased over time with respect to a set point (pH 5), represented by a red dotted line in both
 67 graphs. To overcome their pH buffer capacity (thus reaching a stable pH 5 in the aqueous
 68 medium), granules were subjected to consecutive washing cycles with 0.45% (w/v) NaCl at pH
 69 5 (*: liquid bulk substitution), ensuring a total contact time in the range of 100-400 hours
 70 dependent on the granule concentration.

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72 **Table S2** – Literature survey of sorbent and biosorbent media used for copper removal.

	pH (-)	Initial metal concentration (mg/L)	Adsorption capacity (mg/g)	References
Clay				
Bentonite clay (after calcification 400 °C)	5	90	11.89	Bertagnolli et al., 2011
Bofe bentonite calcinated clay	4.5	100	19.06	de Almeida Neto et al., 2014
Magnetic adsorbents				
Sulfonated graphene oxide composite	4.68	73.71	63.73	Hu et al., 2013
Pectin-coated iron oxide magnetic nanocomposite	-		48.99	Gong et al., 2012
Hyaluronic acid-supported magnetic microspheres	6.8	50	12.2	Lan et al., 2013
Alumina				
γ-alumina nanoparticles	5	200	31.3	Fouladgar et al., 2015
3 new alumina adsorbents of acidic, neutral and basic nature	7	1	27.96, 28.58, 28.59	Mahmoud et al., 2010
Aminated/protonated mesoporous alumina	-	20	7.92/14.53	Rengaraj et al., 2004
Fungal biomass				
<i>Chlorella</i> sp. and <i>Chlamydomonas</i> sp.	7	5	33.4	Wan Maznah et al., 2012
<i>Rhizopus oryzae</i> filamentous fungus	6	200	19.4	Bhainsa and D'Souza, 2008
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> biomass	5	100	20.62	Mukhopadhyay et al., 2007
Algal biomass				
Macroalga, <i>Sargassum muticum</i>	4.5	190	71	Herrero et al., 2011
Dried micro-algal/bacterial biomass	4	1000	31	Loutseti et al., 2009
<i>Codium vermilara</i>	5	150	16.52	Romera et al., 2007
Yeast biomass				
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> biomass	5	200	2.59	Cojocararu et al., 2009
ETDAD-modified biomass of baker's yeast	6	100	65	Yu et al., 2008
Bacteria				
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	5	64	10.36	Ravikumar et al., 2011
<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp. (DSM 20057)	6	39.8	0.046	Schut et al., 2011
<i>Pseudomonas stutzeri</i>	5	100	36.2	Hassan et al., 2009

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75 **Table S3** – Literature survey of granular biomasses (AGS: aerobic granular sludge; AnGS:
 76 anaerobic granular sludge; AnmGS: anammox granular sludge) used as biosorbent media for the
 77 heavy metal removal. Q_{max} values (mg/g) are related to the theoretical maximum adsorption
 78 capacities interfered by Langmuir adsorption isotherm model.

Biosorbent	Heavy metals	pH	Q_{max} (mg/g)	References
AnGS	Lead, Copper, Nickel	5.5	286, 60, 25	Hawari and Mulligan (2006)
AGS	Copper	5	36.72	Gai et al. (2008)
AGS	Zinc	5	64.44	Wei et al. (2016)
AGS	Nickel	7	28	Xu et al. (2006)
AGS; AnGS	Nickel	4	65.77 (AGS) 54.18 (AnGs)	Li et al. (2017)
AnmGS ^[1]	Lead, Copper, Nickel, Zinc	5-6	103.7, 36.1, 48.2, 48.9	Present study

79 ^[1] Q_{max} values (mg/g) related to the maximum adsorption capacities obtained under the tested experimental
 80 conditions ($C_0=500$ mg/L), given that the equilibrium sorption data were not well correlated by Langmuir model.

81 **Table S4** - Model parameters and statistical indicators related to the fitting of anammox EPS
82 and granule equilibrium sorption data via Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherm models.
83 R^2 values reported in the table are the coefficients of determination, where R represents the
84 correlation coefficient $R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (z_i - z_m)(w_i - w_m)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (z_i - z_m)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (w_i - w_m)^2}}$ (z_i and z_m are the observed values and
85 their average value, respectively, while w_i and w_m are the predicted values and their average
86 value, respectively). The data fitting was done using the software Igor Pro. Model parameters
87 reported in the table are expressed as average values \pm standard deviation.

Anammox EPS							
	<i>Langmuir adsorption isotherms</i>				<i>Freundlich adsorption isotherms</i>		
	Q_m (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R_L (-)	R^2	K_f (L/g)	n (-)	R^2
Pb ²⁺	82.47 \pm 10.10	0.385 \pm 0.184	0.005	0.927	19.80 \pm 3.69	2.37 \pm 0.34	0.942
Cu ²⁺	58.73 \pm 5.03	0.030 \pm 0.008	0.063	0.974	4.83 \pm 1.62	2.16 \pm 0.33	0.953
Ni ²⁺	29.02 \pm 2.92	0.008 \pm 0.002	0.200	0.984	0.89 \pm 0.24	1.83 \pm 0.16	0.985
Zn ²⁺	13.40 \pm 3.02	0.004 \pm 0.001	0.369	0.986	0.14 \pm 0.11	1.47 \pm 0.30	0.958
Anammox granules							
	<i>Langmuir adsorption isotherms</i>				<i>Freundlich adsorption isotherms</i>		
	Q_m (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R_L (-)	R^2	K_f (L/g)	n (-)	R^2
Pb ²⁺	90.03 \pm 9.37	0.790 \pm 0.600	0.004	0.925	41.18 \pm 3.27	6.29 \pm 0.64	0.941
Cu ²⁺	39.18 \pm 8.22	0.018 \pm 0.012	0.100	0.948	6.15 \pm 0.76	3.48 \pm 0.28	0.990
Ni ²⁺	59.41 \pm 22.8	0.006 \pm 0.005	0.211	0.851	5.49 \pm 2.75	2.98 \pm 0.82	0.866
Zn ²⁺	69.07 \pm 32.8	0.005 \pm 0.004	0.280	0.938	6.70 \pm 4.44	3.17 \pm 1.20	0.903

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90 **Figure S4** – FT-IR spectra of EPS samples before and after heavy metal sorption tests obtained
 91 in the transmission mode using a BioRad FTS-40 spectrometer (4 cm⁻¹ resolution, 64 scans,
 92 spectral range 2000–400 cm⁻¹, DTGS detector). Peak assignment according to Lotti et al. (2019)
 93 and Niu et al. (2016).

94 EPS spectra presented some changes in terms of peak shifts after the interaction with heavy
 95 metal ions. The highest shifts were observed for the peaks at 1547 cm⁻¹ (→ 1537, 1536, 1537
 96 and 1535 cm⁻¹ after Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ adsorption, respectively), related to C-N stretching
 97 and N-H bending (proteins, Amide II), and 1047 cm⁻¹ (→ 1074, 1058, 1076 and 1074 cm⁻¹ after
 98 Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ adsorption, respectively), assigned to C-H in plane bending
 99 (polysaccharides). The metal-binding capability of Anammox EPS might be therefore
 100 associated to polysaccharide- and protein-like substances.

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102 **Figure S5** – Surface morphology of composite EPS-Pb aggregates (precipitated in single-metal
 103 sorption tests at $C_0=500$ mg/L) observed through a scanning electron microscope (SEM Zeiss
 104 Evo MA15) at different magnifications (57X, **a**; 1000X, **b**) and corresponding elemental
 105 compositions detected by energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDS Oxford Inca 250) in two
 106 points of analysis reported as example (c). The Au peaks are due to the sample coating with
 107 gold prior to SEM/EDS analysis.

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109 **Figure S6** – Surface morphology of composite EPS-Cu aggregates (precipitated in single-metal
 110 sorption tests at $C_0=500$ mg/L) observed through a scanning electron microscope (SEM Zeiss
 111 Evo MA15) at different magnifications (57X, **a**; 1000X, **b**) and corresponding elemental
 112 compositions detected by energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDS Oxford Inca 250) in two
 113 point of analysis reported as example (**c**). The Au peaks are due to the sample coating with gold
 114 prior to SEM/EDS analysis.

115 **Table S5** – Ionic strength (μ , mM) of EPS- M^{2+} mixed aqueous systems (M^{2+} =Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺
 116 and Zn²⁺, respectively) in single-sorbate sorption tests performed with increasing initial metal
 117 concentration ($[M^{2+}]$, mM). pH of the polymer-metal aqueous dispersions was adjusted to 5-6
 118 adding 0.1 NaOH/1M HCl.

EPS-Pb aqueous systems (pH 5)		EPS-Cu aqueous systems (pH 5)	
$[M^{2+}]$ (mM)	μ (mM)	$[M^{2+}]$ (mM)	μ (mM)
0.02	16.50	0.08	25.24
0.05	20.22	0.17	28.29
0.11	20.40	0.36	28.86
0.22	20.75	1.49	22.42
0.47	26.23	3.18	22.27
0.98	23.00	4.46	22.72
2.02	21.25	6.09	27.59
2.58	21.70	7.76	30.63
EPS-Ni aqueous systems (pH 6)		EPS-Zn aqueous systems (pH 6)	
$[M^{2+}]$ (mM)	μ (mM)	$[M^{2+}]$ (mM)	μ (mM)
0.09	7.39	0.07	13.11
0.19	7.68	0.15	10.86
0.39	8.29	0.31	23.54
0.80	9.51	0.61	14.71
1.59	11.90	1.19	15.46
3.11	16.44	2.60	20.67
5.06	22.29	3.92	19.69
8.59	32.88	6.55	29.81

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122 **Figure S7** - Hydrodynamic diameter and Zeta-potential of aqueous solution (pH 8) containing
 123 0.01% (w/v) anammox EPS and increasing concentration of Pb^{2+} (a, b, respectively) and Cu^{2+}
 124 (c, d, respectively), detected by using Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) at 90° and Phase
 125 Analysis Light Scattering, respectively (90Plus PALS, Brookhaven Instruments Corporation,
 126 USA). The increase of Pb^{2+} concentration resulted in a strong increase of EPS particle size, and
 127 in a reduction of the repulsive force among EPS units, thus leading to aggregation.

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